

Conference Abstract

Phylogenetic Systematics of Pterostichites (Carabidae)

Kipling Will ‡

‡ University of California, Berkeley, Berkeley, CA, United States of America

Corresponding author: Kipling Will (kipwill@berkeley.edu)

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Abstract

As typically comprised, Pterostichitae includes about 10% of the species described in Carabidae. The phylogenetic study of the family Carabidae headed up by D. Maddison (OSU) that includes 550 carabid species covers all major clades of pterostichites and their putative relatives in Harpalinae. I will present results for the Pterostichitae from that analysis, focusing on relationships among major clades in the Northern Hemisphere (Pterostichina, Zabrina, Sphodrina) and the placement of more distantly related taxa (e.g., Abacetini, Drimostomatini). As analyses of the data have not yet been completed, there will be additional discoveries this summer, about which I will report in my talk.

Presenting author

Kipling Will

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